

Organo-mercury Derivatives of Maleins

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Malein dyes, similar to phthaleins and fluoresceins, have been prepared by condensing maleic anhydride with different phenols. Mercury derivatives of the maleins and the bromo derivatives of the mercury compounds have also been prepared and their antiseptic actions on *Staph. aureus* and *Bact. coli* studied.

The present investigation forms a general survey¹ for the search of new antiseptic compounds of the mercurochrome type and describes the preparation of a number of new organo-mercury compounds for the purpose. Webster and Kamstra² prepared a few maleins by using SnCl_4 as a condensing agent; Dass and Tewari³ and Rao *et al.*⁴ also prepared similar malein dyes by using different condensing agents. By modifying the method of preparation and using concentrated sulphuric acid as the condensing agent, some of these compounds have been obtained in better yields. These dyes on mercuration furnished the corresponding organo-mercury compounds. The latter on demercuration with bromine yielded the corresponding bromo derivatives, depending on the number of acetoxymercuri group introduced during the process of mercuration. The antiseptic action of the sodium salts of these dyes and their mercury derivatives has been determined and compared with that of the mercurochrome. Two types of maleins have been obtained:

In

Resorcinolmalein:	$R_1 = R_2 = R_4 = \text{H}; R_3 = \text{OH}.$
Orcinolmalein:	$R_1 = \text{Me}; R_2 = R_4 = \text{H}; R_3 = \text{OH}.$
Phloroglucinolmalein:	$R_1 = R_3 = \text{OH}; R_2 = R_4 = \text{H}.$
Pyrogallolmalein:	$R_1 = R_4 = \text{H}; R_3 = R_2 = \text{OH}.$
Catecholmalein:	$R_1 = R_4 = R_3 = \text{H}; R_2 = \text{OH}.$

1. Rohatgi, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1958, 21, 117.

2. *Proc. S. Dakala Acad. Sci.*, 1947, 30, 40.

3. *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1941, 13A, 68.

4. *Ibid.*, 1947, 26A, 299.

In

Phenolmalein:	$R_3 = \text{OH}; R_1 = R_2 = R_4 = R_5 = \text{H}.$
<i>o</i> -Cresolmalein:	$R_3 = \text{OH}; R_4 = \text{Me}; R_1 = R_2 = R_5 = \text{H}.$
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenolmalein:	$R_3 = \text{OH}; R_4 = \text{Cl}; R_1 = R_2 = R_5 = \text{H}.$

EXPERIMENTAL

Orcinolmalein.—An intimate mixture of maleic anhydride (2.45 g.) and orcinol (7.3 g.) was heated to 120-30° for 4 hr. in presence of H_2SO_4 (conc., 4-5 drops) in an oil bath. The condensed product after cooling was extracted with dilute NaOH solution and filtered. The malein was then precipitated by adding HCl (dil.) in small portions to the alkaline filtrate. The precipitated malein was filtered and again dissolved in alkaline solution. This process was repeated two or three times. The product, thus obtained, was finally crystallised from ethanol in orange-red crystals and dried at 100° in an electric oven. It blackens at 235° and melts at 242°; it dissolves in ethanol with a reddish yellow colour. (Found: C, 69.01; H, 4.85. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 69.66; H, 4.54%). Table I records the properties of these dyes.

TABLE I

S.No.	Dyes.	Colour.	M.P.	Formula.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1.	Phenolmalein	Colorless(straw)	198°	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$	71.71	71.64	4.67	4.50
2.	<i>o</i> -Cresolmalein	Dark brown	230°	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$	72.28	72.95	6.08	5.49
3.	Catecholmalein	Black	> 300°	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5$	68.45	68.08	3.53	3.57
4.	Resorcinolmalein	Yellow-red	280°	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5$	67.51	68.08	3.12	3.57
5.	Orcinolmalein	Reddish yellow	242°	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$	69.01	69.66	4.84	4.54
6.	Pyrogallolmalein	Black	> 300°	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_7$	60.64	61.15	3.05	3.20
7.	Phloroglucinolmalein	Red-brown	> 300°	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_7$	60.92	61.15	3.40	3.20
8.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenolmalein	Black	> 300°	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_9\text{O}_5\text{Cl}_2$	56.61	56.99	2.82	2.98

N.B. %Chlorine in No. 8. Found: 20.77; calc. 21.03.

Organo-mercury Derivatives.—The mercury derivatives of these dyes were prepared by using the method of White⁵. The process of mercuration proceeded in the normal way, affording organo-mercury compounds containing more than one acetoxymercuri group, depending on the number of free hydroxyl groups in the dyes. The estimated %Hg's in the mercurated dyes are recorded in Table II.

Bromo Derivatives of Mercurated Dyes.—To the mercury derivatives of the dyes, dissolved in acetic acid, calculated amounts of bromine in acetic acid and potassium bro-

mide were added and the mixture was shaken. The bromo compounds were formed by replacing acetoxymercuri group in the dye. On estimating bromine it was found to be the same as the number of mercury atoms. The bromo derivatives were recrystallised from EtOH. The colour, m. p., and analytical data are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

*No.	Mercury derivatives.		*Bromo compounds.					
	Formula.	Colour.	%Mercury.		Formula.	Colour.	%Bromine.	
			Found.	Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.
1.	$C_{16}H_{10}O_4(Hg.O.O.C.CH_3)_2$	Dark brown	52.16	51.18	$C_{16}H_{10}O_4Br_2$	Yellowish grey	36.87	37.53
2.	$C_{18}H_{14}O_4(Hg.O.O.C.CH_3)_2$	„	49.28	49.43	$C_{18}H_{14}O_4Br_2$	Dark brown	35.40	36.22
3.	$C_{16}H_8O_5(Hg.O.O.C.CH_3)_2$	Black	50.61	50.20	$C_{16}H_8O_5Br_2$	Red-brown	36.69	36.36
4.	$C_{15}H_6O_5(Hg.O.O.C.CH_3)_4$	Red-orange	60.40	60.87	$C_{15}H_6O_5Br_4$	Orange-red	53.60	53.45
5.	$C_{18}H_{10}O_5(Hg.O.O.C.CH_3)_4$	Dark orange	50.19	59.68	$C_{18}H_{10}O_5Br_4$	Orange	51.20	51.12
6.	$C_{16}H_8O_7(Hg.O.O.C.CH_3)_2$	Black	48.01	48.38	$C_{16}H_8O_7Br_2$	Dark brown	34.00	34.04
7.	$C_{16}H_6O_7(Hg.O.O.C.CH_3)_4$	Violet-black	59.58	60.24	$C_{16}H_6O_7Br_4$	Red-brown	59.41	59.79
8.	$C_{16}H_8O_4Cl_2(Hg.O.O.C.CH_3)_2$	Dark brown	47.03	49.96	$C_{16}H_8O_4Br_2Cl_2$	Dirty yellow-red	32.11	32.37

*The number corresponds to the dyes in Table I. Bromo derivatives melted above 300°.

Bactericidal Action.—The sodium salts of the dyes and their mercury derivatives were prepared by dissolving the dyes and their mercury derivatives in calculated amounts of NaOH solution. Their bactericidal actions on *Staph. aureus* and *Bact. coli* were determined by finding the number of mg./ml of the sodium salt required to check the growth of one loopful of 24 hr.-broth culture, as recorded in Table III. The sodium salts of the organo-mercury derivatives have been found to possess a far greater bactericidal activity than the sodium salts of the dyes. Further, the sodium salts of the mercury derivatives of phenolmalein, *o*-cresolmalein, *o*-chlorophenolmalein, and catecholmalein exhibit good bactericidal activity, compared with that of mercurochrome.

TABLE III

No.	Maleins.	No. of mg./ml of solum compound reqd. to check the growth of one loopful of 24hr.-broth culture.			
		Dyes.		Mercurated dyes.	
		<i>S. aureus.</i>	<i>Bact. coli.</i>	<i>S. aureus.</i>	<i>Bact. coli.</i>
1.	Phenolmalein	10.00	10.00	0.156	0.312
2.	<i>o</i> -Cresolmalein	1.25	10.00	0.312	0.156
3.	Catecholmalein	2.50	2.50	0.312	0.078
4.	Resorcinolmalein	10.00	5.00	0.312	0.635
5.	Orcinolmalein	5.00	20.00	0.625	2.500
6.	Pyrogallolmalein	1.25	1.25	0.312	0.625
7.	Phloroglucinolmalein	1.25	2.50	0.312	0.312
8.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenolmalein	2.50	20.00	0.078	0.156
9.	Mercurochrome	..	..	0.078	0.156

The authors are thankful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for sanctioning the scheme on the study of bactericidal activity of mercury compounds, providing necessary grants, and the award of a research fellowship to one of them (A. N. Agarwal).